

Education Quarterly Reviews

Wiisahnyuy, Lilian F., and Bodang, Pierrina Miyanui. (2020), An Assessment of History Teaching Strategies and Promotion of Professional Diversity in Public High Schools in Mezam, Cameroon. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.3, No.1, 23-36.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.03.01.115

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

An Assessment of History Teaching Strategies and Promotion of Professional Diversity in Public High Schools in Mezam, Cameroon

Lilian F. Wiysahnyuy, (Ph.D.)¹, Pierrina Miyanui Bodang, (M.Ed)²

¹Higher Teacher Training College, the University of Bamenda. Email: fai_lilian@yahoo.com

²Faculty of Arts, the University of Bamenda, Cameroon. Email: mpierrina@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

There is a misconception that History as an academic subject centers on the mere recitation of the past which may have nothing to do with socio-professional insertion and diversity. In Cameroon, it is common to see post secondary school leavers with majors in History postulating in over bearing numbers, usually over a thousand for less than fifty places in public competitive examinations organized by the state for the admission and training of pre-service History educators. It is on this backdrop that this paper was designed to examine the relationship between History teaching strategies and professional diversity in some public schools in Mezam Division. The correlation design was used in this study since it was intended to examine the relationship between teaching strategies and professional diversity. The simple random and purposive sampling techniques were used to select a sample size of 260 and 31 second cycle History students and teachers, respectively drawn from some 13 public schools in Mezam Division. Two sets of questionnaire were used to collect the data. The data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient. After analysing the data, it was realised that majority of the History teachers frequently used the direct teaching strategy which hindered students aspiration for diverse professions. The findings revealed from the inferences that the indirect and interactive strategies could have a positive relationship with professional diversity if History teachers effectively use them. Therefore History teachers should diversify their teaching strategies giving priority to the indirect and interactive strategies which encourage learners' creativity, positive transfer of learning and development of skills which could enhance learners' aspirations for diverse professions.

Keywords: Diversity, History, Teaching, Professional, Strategy

1. Introduction

Teaching entails facilitation of learning which can be effectively carried out using diverse strategies to get desired effect. Among the pool of subjects in the secondary school education programme that elicits students' interest and enlistment, History stands out distinct. This is perhaps due to the fact that, it is a major subject in the group of disciplines of the Arts and Humanities options (A1, A2, A3 and A5) at the second cycle of Cameroon Secondary schools. The primary objective of this subject bias is to socialise the students with general historical knowledge especially with adept knowledge on Cameroon and African past experiences which could serve as a lever to appreciate the present and project the future course of actions. Given this context, the most probable perception of students introduced to historical science is to graduate to a purveyor of historical knowledge. This indicates that the graduate assumes the role of a history educator as that of a university lecturer posing in front of students

in a class equipped with maps and a chalk board delivering lectures to an audience of undergraduates (Schulze et al, 2002). This does not dispute the fact that historians have the calling to teach about the past. The reality in the study of History is lost in the erroneous view that it is simply the study of the past. This view is held even by teachers who tend to attach little or no importance to the way History as an academic discipline is taught therefore limiting learners' perception of the subject. Many History students in Cameroon hold that the study of History will limit them to History educators. This is justified by the impressive number of students who register to write the competitive entrance examination into Higher Teacher Training College in the Department of History and the number of students who register to study History in the University. This is because most of the teaching of History has been reduced to a recitation of the past that has little or no application to the daily lives of most students (Weiner, 1995). Ironically, the study of History offers diverse opportunities as far as professional avenues are concerned. This is not known and understood by History teachers and students in most public secondary schools in Cameroon in general and Mezam in particular. Other countries such as the United State of America have realized that Historical study plays an important part in fostering well-grounded intellectual development as well as instilling valuable career skills in research, writing, argumentation and documentation over the years. This is seen in the case where persons who study History offer excellent preparation for careers in law, journalism, public relations, technical writing, fundraising, administration, government service and even medicine. Cameroon is yet to realize the possibility of promoting professional diversity through the teaching of History. Could this be as result of the teaching strategies which some teachers use in teaching History? It is for this reason that this paper seeks to investigate the link between History teaching strategies and professional diversity.

2. Background of the study

History has been recognized all over the world as a source of enlightenment and development, (Oyerami, 2011). Elucidating further, Nasson (2002) holds that History is the study of the past in order to understand the meaning and dynamics of the relationship between the cause and effect in the overall development of human sciences to better the future. It is obvious here that a non-debatable advantage in the study of History is the acquisition of a variety of skills that are essential requisites for different demands in different job market. In the case of Cameroon, the main objective of teaching History in secondary Schools as couched by the Cameroon General Certificate Examination Board (CGCEB), is to produce historians with critical minds equipped with the skills of analysis, evaluation and synthesis of historical events and to encourage the application of the acquired knowledge to local situations. These objectives important and captivating as they appear can best be realized if premium is given to the choice of teaching strategies required to impart and impact the subject. History teaching strategies within formal milieus have evolved considerably over time and circumstances often influenced by available opportunities and persistent constraints in a technological advancing contemporary world. Adom, Adam & Agyemmag (2016) define strategy as a planned series of actions which the teacher intends to implement to make the teaching and learning activities effective in the classroom. This implies that teaching strategies are those basic procedures implemented by the teacher to ensure effective teaching and learning. More so, History teaching strategies differ from one geographical, political and socio-cultural environment to another. This is added to the fact that different environments have learners with diverse needs. Dulfer, Mckernan & Brindle (2016) hold that there is need for the use of differentiated instruction to support diverse student needs. Meeting the needs of these learners, is indirectly meeting the present and future needs of the society.

The teaching of History in Africa at large is without doubt a duty and obligation given it varied importance. According to Ebot (2008), South African Historians argued that the teaching of History is central to the promotion of human values and morality since it studies records and diffuses knowledge of human failures and achievements over time. As a scientific discipline, its exploitation and transmission have been done informally and formally. Informally mediums like stories, drama, myth and fables have been used over time. Gradually, formal patterns employed without necessarily supplanting the informal ways of appropriating the values of the discipline. By the end of the 20th century, History was taught as a compulsory subject in most African countries. Saphir, (2001) using the case of Ghana states that, initially History was taught using the direct teaching strategy which is considered as a teacher centered approach where the students are very passive during the lessons. This made History to be referred to as a "dull" and "dry" subject. In an attempt to wipe out this faulty impression, the interactive approach was introduced and is gradually being implemented by the use of discussion, group work, question and answer

with the aim of arousing students' interest and participation in the subject. Aligning in this view, Adejunmobi, (1975), maintains that the teaching of History was accepted in Nigeria from the introduction of formal education but History in Nigeria is still seen by many, especially learners as merely the study of past events. Olajide (2012) blames this on the inadequate and ineffective use of instructional strategies by History teachers in Nigeria who frequently use the direct teaching strategy to the detriment of other strategies. Methods such as lecture and explanations dominate the teaching learning process. This does not give enough room for learners' participation and involvement in the lesson and therefore may not motivate desires towards professional diversity which is one of the essential outputs of the teaching-learning transaction.

Professional knowledge and decisions invariable influence all facets of modern life and have come to dominate the essence of the world. Given the complexity of human exigencies, professional knowledge is very diverse. Professional diversity here depicts the ability to indulge into different fields and professions other than History teaching after studying History. This is possible depending on the strategies implemented in the teaching process. Different strategies will orientate the learner's view and perception of the subject and other professions. History teaching and learning skewed towards professional diversity provides an opportunity for learners to acquire skills and values necessary to impact the society through a variety of professions. The Western World, conscious of this importance was quick in understanding and using varied strategies in teaching History. Wiersma (2008) in an empirical investigation on Canada noticed that, many teaching methods including the lecture, case study, discussion, tutoring, inquiry, simulation, gaming and programmed instruction are used in teaching History. Pangalangan (2008) reveals that the intersection of art and cognitive science in a complementary approach provides mutual support in teaching History which enhances learners' divergent thinking. Durkee (2017) for his part contends that Americans are not taught their History but their culture. Despite this claim, History teachers use varied teaching strategies blended with media to pass on knowledge while meeting the needs of the learners and society. This gives learners a positive view on the subject and thus exposes them to the various opportunities offered by this high-status subject. Clarke (2019) admits that she uses video to give her students a break from reading, writing and other classroom activities. Cartwright (2019) exposes how she uses social media to assist her History students in acquiring diverse skills. The use of various factual materials makes it possible not only for the range of learner's conception of the historical past but also to influence their attitude and emotions towards the subject. All these show how diversify some teachers especially in the developed world are in the teaching of History which could enhance the professional diversity of the learners. According to Volgograd (2000), developed countries understood this a long time ago while developing countries especially in Africa are still working on this. Therefore this paper seeks to examine the relationship between the teaching strategies used by Secondary school teachers in Cameroon and students aspiration for professional diversity.

2.1 Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between direct teaching strategy and professional diversity?
2. What is the link between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity?
3. What position does interactive teaching strategy hold in professional diversity?

2.2 Research Hypotheses

- H_{a1}:- Direct teaching strategy has a significant relationship with professional diversity
H_{o1}:- Direct teaching strategy has no significant relationship with professional diversity
H_{a2}:- There is a significant relationship between indirect teaching and professional diversity
H_{o2}:- There is no significant relationship between indirect teaching and professional diversity
H_{a3}:- Interactive teaching strategy has a significantly relationship with professional diversity.
H_{o3}:- Interactive teaching strategy has not significantly relationship to professional diversity.

3. Methods and Procedures

This study adopted the correlation research design which is based on finding out the relationship between variables. The study was designed to find out if there exist any relationship between History teaching strategies and professional diversity. This research was carried out in selected Secondary Schools in Mezam Division in the North West Region of Cameroon. Mezam is made up of seven subdivisions which are Bafut, Bali, Bamenda I, Bamenda II, Bamenda III, Santa and Tubah. One high school was selected from each of the Sub Divisions. Mezam has both confessional and public secondary schools but the research was carried out in public schools. Teachers in public schools are hired from a pool of graduates trained in any of the four Higher Teacher Training colleges in Cameroon. It was on this premise that the researcher imagined the sample of teachers was those who were informed about teaching strategies. The researcher made the choice of Second Cycle students, owing to the fact that they were closest to higher education and at this level, they could make professional choices and start implementing them upon graduation.

The target population of the study comprised of second cycle students and professional teachers in selected schools of the seven Sub-Divisions in Mezam Division. This summed up to 1200 of which were 1110 students and 90 teachers. The choice of population was informed by the statistics gotten from the Regional Delegation of Secondary Education in Bamenda in 2018 at the time of data collection. The accessible population comprised of 748 students and 56 History teachers giving a total of 804 respondents gotten from 15 Public Secondary Schools. The sample size consisted of 260 Second Cycle History students and 31 Second Cycle History teachers gotten from 13 Public High Schools giving a total of 291 respondents following the Krejcie and Morgan table. Simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to obtain 13 Public High Schools in Mezam Division. In Sub Divisions with two and less accessible schools, a purposive sampling technique was used. This technique was used in Bamenda I, III, Bali, Santa and Tubah Sub Division. In Sub Divisions with three and more accessible schools, a simple random sampling technique was used. In selecting students, a simple random sampling technique was also used. A ratio of one to ten students per teacher was considered. This gave a minimum of two and a maximum of four teachers per school. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the teachers. Assistance was solicited and received from the schools' administrations to ensure that the copies of the questionnaire were timely attended to by the most punctual teachers.

Table 1: Sample size

Sub-Division	S/N	School	History Students	Teachers	Total sample Population
Bamenda I		GBHS Bamendankwe	40	4	33
Bamenda II		GBHS Down town	20	3	14
		GBHS Nitop	20	2	16
Bamenda III	4	GBHS Atiela	20	3	18
	5	GBHS Bayelle	20	2	17
Bafut	6	GHS Bafut	20	2	14
	7	GHS Mambu	20	2	13
Bali	8.	GBHS Bali	20	2	20
	9.	GBHS Etoma	20	2	19
Santa	10	GBHS Santa	20	2	21
	11	GHS Buchi	20	2	20

Tubah	12	CCAST Bambili	20	3	27
	13	GHS MachaBambui	20	2	27
Total	13		260	31	291

The main research instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. Two sets of questionnaires were designed for the students and teachers. The Questionnaires were designed to find out the relationship between History teaching strategies and professional diversity from both teachers and students. The instruments were administered in the various classrooms by the researchers. In administering the questionnaire, the researchers employed the help of a research assistant after ascertaining the concerned was an expert in the field. This was to minimize errors at the level of administering the copies of the questionnaire and to guarantee proper assistance from the research assistant. Respondents filled the copies of the questionnaire and returned them without delay. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS) version 20, Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were used. For descriptive statistics, results were presented using frequency distribution tables and charts. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to verify the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. This test was deemed fit for this study because it assesses the degree that quantitative variables are linearly related in a sample.

4. Results and Analysis

This section comprises the responses on the research questions and testing of the hypotheses.

4.1 Research Questions

Research question one. What is the relationship between direct teaching strategy and professional diversity?

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of responses on the use of Direct Teaching Strategy in teaching History

The results on figure 1 show that an overwhelming majority (81%) of teachers agreed that they mostly used the lecture method in teaching history. As far as the explicit teaching strategy was concerned, most of (77%) the teachers consented using it. It was also realised that a slight majority (52%) of teachers accepted that they were the only actors when teaching. Most (53%) of the respondents also stated that students did more of listening during History lessons. With respect to History teachers taking total control of the classroom when teaching, 94% of the teachers agreed. From the foregoing, it is evident that most history teachers use more of the direct teaching strategy which makes learners to become recipients of experiences during the teaching-learning process. With the frequent use of this strategy, learners' knowledge and creative skills are not exploited and this hinders students' exposure to the numerous professional openings offered by the discipline of History.

In order to complement the responses from teachers, students' opinions were also sought on the extent to which their teachers used the direct teaching strategy.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of students whose teachers use direct teaching strategy

The results on figure 2 indicate that majority (>70%) of the students confirmed that their History teachers used mostly the direct strategy in teaching. According to them their history teachers lectured, gave explanations and notes, the teachers were considered as the only actors during the delivery process while students did more of listening. These results corroborate with the results from teachers indicating that History is taught using more of the direct teaching strategy in the selected schools which do not really enhance professional diversity.

Research question two. What is the link between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity?

Figure 3: Frequency distribution of responses on the extent to which teachers use indirect teaching strategy

Based on the two points Likert's scale adopted for the research, the following quantitative results were obtained as indicated on figure 3. The results show that very few teachers (32%) accepted to have ensured learners participation during History Lessons. When asked whether they used dramatization as a teaching method, it was realised that only 29% of the teachers accepted to have used this method in their History Lessons. Also very few teachers (23%) agreed that when teaching History they direct or coach students to construct knowledge. It was realised that an insignificant number (6%) of the teachers accepted to have been using the project method in teaching History. It was equally realised that just a few number (10%) of teachers gave room for students to play roles in History lessons. Drawing from the results, it is indicative that, a majority of History teachers did not use the indirect teaching strategy. This shows that a majority of the teachers used methods of teaching which did not provoke the

learners to construct knowledge and implant in them the skills necessary to use acquired knowledge in solving problems.

Data was also collected from the students to find out the extent to which their teachers used the indirect strategy in teaching history and how it could enhance their professional diversity.

Figure 4: Frequency distribution of students responses on the use of the indirect teaching strategy by History teachers

The results on figure 4 indicate that minority (<30%) of the students confirmed that their History teachers were using the indirect strategy in teaching. In this study, 43% of students agreed that their teachers ensured their participation during lessons, 29% of students acknowledged that their teachers made use of dramatization as a teaching method, 43% of the students accepted that their teachers orientate their questions towards bringing out the right answers from the students while an insignificant number (19%) of students attested that their History teachers gave them projects to carry out in groups. A few number (23%) of the students agreed that their teachers used role play in teaching. This implies that the indirect teaching strategy was not very much used in the selected High schools in Mezam Division. Thereby hindering students' discovery of knowledge and other skills which could enhance professional diversity.

Research Question three: What position does interactive teaching strategy hold in professional diversity?

Figure 5: Teachers responses on interactive teaching strategy

The results on figure 5 indicate that very few History teachers were using the interactive strategy in teaching. Based on the results obtained, few (39%) respondents agreed that they gave room for exchange of ideas between the learner and teacher during the teaching learning transaction. It was realised that only 23% of the teachers accepted that they ensured interaction among the students and equally created a favourable environment for interaction. An insignificant number (10%) of the respondents agreed that they ensured brainstorming among the students when teaching History. The only aspect of the interactive strategy with a slight majority (52%) of teachers indicated that they were using was the discussion method. These results suggest that majority of the History teachers in the selected schools were not using the interactive teaching strategy. Consequently their teaching strategies did not give satisfactory premium to the promotion of professional diversity.

Students' opinions were also sought on the use of interactive teaching strategies by their History teachers. The results are presented in figure 6

Figure 6: Distribution of students whose teachers use the Interactive History Teaching Strategy

The results on figure 6 indicate that the students' responses corroborate teachers' responses which show that History teachers rarely used the interactive strategy. Some (45%) students indicated that their History teacher gave room for the exchange of ideas between the teacher and students. A few (29%) of them accepted that their History teachers encouraged exchange of ideas among students. An insignificant number (14%) of students agreed that their History teachers created a favourable environment for interaction. When quizzed on the use of discussion method in teaching History, very few (8%) students indicated that their teachers made use of it. This gives a contrary view from the teachers' responses because majority of the teachers indicated to have been using this method. The findings stipulate that in the selected High Schools in Mezam, a majority of History teachers do not use the interactive teaching strategy. This means that they do not encourage the development of skills, values and attitudes necessary for the appropriation of varied professional opportunities.

4.2 Professional Diversity

As far as professional diversity is concerned, data was collected from the students to see whether the way history is taught can help them to venture into different professions.

Figure 7. Students responses on professional diversity

In this context where professional diversity means the ability to explore a variety of job openings, the results on figure 7 indicate that more than 60% of the students were of the fact that the way their history teachers were teaching did not enhance professional diversity. From the results, minority (38%) of the students agreed that their History teachers taught and ensured diversity in professionalism. Some (27%) students agreed that their history teachers taught in a manner that set a foundation for professional diversity. A few students (32%) agreed that in teaching History, their teachers drew students' attention to the fact that studying History exposes them to professional openings other than History. Also, some (43%) of the students held that their History teacher taught them such that they were motivated to explore professional openings other than teaching History in secondary schools. From the thesis of these results it is evident that majority of the History teachers in the selected schools were not encouraging professional diversity when teaching. This could be related to the fact that most of the teachers were using the direct strategy of teaching which does not promote discovery learning, skill development and positive transfer of knowledge in everyday life.

4.3 Verification of Hypotheses

This work was guided by the following research hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance

Hypothesis one

H_{a1}:- Direct teaching strategy has a significant relationship with professional diversity

H_{o1}:- Direct teaching strategy has no significant relationship with professional diversity

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for Hypothesis one

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Direct teaching strategy	24.6474	3.63038	291
Professional diversity	22.3382	4.62928	291

Table 1 shows that there is a mean difference that exist between Direct Teaching Strategy (M=24.65, SD=3.63, N=291) and Professional Diversity (M=22.34, SD=4.63, N=291)

Table 2. Inferential statistics on direct teaching strategy and professional diversity

Correlations	Direct teaching strategy	Professional diversity	
Direct teaching strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	-.776**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	4546.983	1600.254
	Covariance	13.180	4.638
	N	291	291
Professional diversity	Pearson Correlation	-.776**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1600.254	7393.436
	Covariance	4.638	21.430
	N	291	291

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A two tailed correlation matrix using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to inter-match the correlation indices of the predictor and the criterion variables. The results from table 2 reveal that there is a significant negative relationship ($r=-0.78$, $df=289$, $p=0.001<0.01$) between direct teaching strategy and professional diversity. This correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), an indication of the fact that the more teachers use the direct teaching strategy during the teaching-learning transaction the lesser they will be promoting professional diversity among learners. The calculated value of the Pearson product moment correlation is greater than the critical value ($r_{cal}=-0.78>r_{crit}=0.15$), based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is retained. This means that there is a significant negative relationship between the direct teaching strategy and professional diversity among students

Hypothesis two

H_{a2}:-There is a significant relationship between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity

H_{o2}:- There is no significant relationship between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for hypothesis two

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Indirect teaching strategy	28.6387	5.72239	291
Professional diversity	22.3382	4.62928	291

The results on table 3 reveals a mean difference that exist between indirect teaching strategy (M=28.64, SD=5.72, N=291) and professional diversity (M=22.34, SD=4.63, N=291)

Table 1: Inferential statistics on indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity

Correlations	Indirect teaching strategy	professional diversity	
Indirect teaching strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.707**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000

	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	7693.841	2541.269
	Covariance	22.301	7.366
	N	291	291
Professional diversity	Pearson Correlation	.707**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	2541.269	7393.436
	Covariance	7.366	21.430
	N	291	291

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the two tailed correlation matrix using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to inter-match the correlation indices of the predictor and the criterion variables, a significant positive relationship ($r=0.71$, $df=289$, $p=0.001<0.01$) between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity was inferred. The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). This brings to light the fact that the use of the indirect teaching strategy by History teachers will help in promoting professional diversity in their learners. The calculated value for Pearson was greater than the critical value ($r_{cal}=0.71>r_{crit}=0.15$), with regard to the decision rule, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is retained. Therefore, there is a significant positive relationship between indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity. This implies that if History teachers use the indirect strategy of teaching effectively it will enhance professional diversity of History students.

Hypothesis Three

H_{a3}:- Interactive teaching strategy significantly relates to professional diversity

H_{o3}:- Interactive teaching strategy does not significantly relates to professional diversity

Table 5: Descriptive statistics for hypothesis three

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Interactive teaching strategy	30.4971	4.30116	291
professional diversity	22.3382	4.62928	291

The descriptive statistics on table 5 indicates that there is a mean difference between interactive teaching strategy ($M=30.50$, $SD=4.30$, $N=291$) and professional diversity ($M=22.34$, $SD=4.63$, $N=291$).

Table 6: Inferential statistics on interactive teaching strategy and professional diversity

Correlations		Interactive teaching strategy	professional diversity
Interactive Teaching Strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.682*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.011
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	6382.497	943.838
	Covariance	18.500	2.736
	N	291	291
Professional Diversity	Pearson Correlation	.682*	1

Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	
Sum of Squares and Cross-products	943.838	7393.436
Covariance	2.736	21.430
N	291	291

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

A two tailed correlation matrix using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to inter-match the correlation indices of the predictor and the criterion variables were computed. A significant positive relationship ($r=0.68$, $df=289$, $p=0.01<0.05$) between interactive teaching strategy and professional diversity was established. The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). This shows that the more teachers apply the interactive teaching strategy the more it will enhance learners' professional diversity. The calculated value for Pearson was seen to be greater than the critical value ($r_{cal}=0.68>r_{crit}=0.11$), taking a standpoint from the decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was retained; therefore it is inferred that there is a significant positive relationship between interactive teaching strategy and professional diversity. This shows that History teachers need to use more of the interactive teaching strategy in order to enhance learners' professional diversity.

5. Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study was to bring out the link between History teaching strategies and Professional Diversity. The findings of this study are discussed based on the objectives of the study.

5.1 Direct teaching strategy and professional diversity

The study revealed that many teachers used the lecture method in teaching History. Teachers were the main actors when teaching History. In most History classes, students do more of listening during the teaching-learning transaction than active participation in the lesson construction. This is understandably because the teachers usually arrogate absolute control during the teaching-learning process. The empirical work of Williams and Keikkar (1973), motivates this view when they opine that a majority of the teachers do not ensure learner's participation during history lessons and they do not use drama as a method in teaching history lessons. The results of this study corroborate the work of Wiysahnyuy (2019) which states that teachers **tend to use direct methods like lecture illustration, so as to complete their scheme of work for the given class which hinders the learning process of some learners and discourages diversity**. The findings of the study reveal that direct teaching strategy is negatively associated with the promotion of professional diversity among History students. When teachers use the direct strategy in teaching, learners become very passive and this affects their creative abilities which could help them to aspire for diverse professions. Tchombe (2009) further maintains that direct teaching strategy encourages rote learning which is far from what is required in the twenty first century. This approach also does not tie with Brunner's (1960) theory of discovery learning which states that, learning through practice and discovery teaches one to acquire information in a way that makes the information more readily viable in problem solving. It was realized that the use of direct teaching strategy by teachers do not enhance professional diversity as most teachers did not help students to think out of the boxes. Teachers who use this strategy find it difficult to make learners understand the importance of the knowledge they are acquiring. This goes in line with the findings of Wiysahnyuy (2019) which states that most teachers in public schools in Bamenda municipality focus on the transmission of information but do not help the students to appreciate the importance of the knowledge they are acquiring. This invariably makes the learners to be less diversified as far as professional opportunities are concerned.

5.2 Indirect teaching strategy and professional diversity

It was realized from the study that a greater percentage of teachers do not ensure learners' participation during History lessons. More so, a majority of History teachers do not direct or coach students to construct knowledge when teaching history. Few History teachers use project teaching as a method. Also, few History teachers give room for students to play roles during lessons. This means that a lesser percentage of teachers make use of the indirect teaching strategy. This is an indication that although teachers are trained on how to teach history, they still find it difficult to implement some of the strategies which can enhance learners' participation in the teaching learning process. This may be one of the reasons most history students aspire only to become teachers and rarely think of other professions in the Cameroon context. The findings reveal that the indirect teaching strategy has a significant positive relationship with learner's professional diversity. This means that if History teachers could use the indirect teaching strategies it will help learners to aspire for diverse professions. This is in line with Shinn (1997) who states that there is a significant statistical difference among groups when teachers use problem solving approaches which help learners to be diversified in their thinking in relation to career choices. This is also backed by Rutmann & Kipper (2011) who concluded their research by saying that when used with the appropriate content and purpose, indirect teaching strategy can significantly improve teaching effectiveness and positive transfer of Knowledge.

5.3 Interactive teaching strategy in professional diversity

A greater percentage of teachers do not ensure the exchange of ideas between students and themselves or between students and students. Many teachers do not create favourable environment for interaction during History lessons or ensure brain storming among students. This is in line with Mohammad (1988) who developed and evaluated a modulated individualized instruction science in Kuwait secondary schools. His study revealed that a greater percentage of the teachers do not ensure interaction between students and other students as shown by the study. Again from the study, it was revealed that teachers do not create a favourable environment for interaction and brainstorming among students. Verification of hypothesis 3 revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between interactive teaching strategy and the incubation of professional diversity. This means that if teachers use the interactive teaching strategy, they will certainly promote professional diversity.

6. Conclusion

The study developed from a concern in Cameroon Public Secondary Schools where several High School graduates with majors in History were innocent to find professional opportunities emanating from the lessons and practice of History. It was quickly diagnosed that the problem was stemming from inadequate teaching approaches. It was premised on this psycho-pedagogic issue that the study sets out to examine the relationship between History teaching strategies and professional diversity. The study sought specifically to investigate the relationship between direct, indirect and interactive teaching strategies and professional diversity. With the aid of questionnaires it was discovered that there is a negative relationship between the direct teaching strategy and professional diversity. The findings also revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between the indirect and interactive teaching strategies and professional diversity. The findings indicated further that the strategies used in teaching History will influence learner's perception on professional openings offered by the study of History.

It was principally noticed that the direct teaching strategy was commonly used in the teaching of History. Based on the findings of this study, the strategy is not favourable for the promotion of professional diversity. The study projects the indirect and interactive teaching strategies as those which will incubate professional diversity. This is because these strategies involve the learners in the learning process and go further to incubate required skills, attitude and values required for problem solving in the society. Knowing which strategy to use and when to use is very important. Using the right strategy at the right time and place inculcates skills and values in learners which for sure are necessary for the development of the society. It is necessary for teachers to use a combination of the teaching strategies especially the indirect and interactive strategies in order to enhance learners' discovery of knowledge, positive transfer of learning and development of skills which are all necessary for professional diversity.

References

- Adom, D. Adam, S & Agyemang, O. (2016) *Effective Instructional methods and strategies for teaching Art History-International Journal of Art and Art History* (Vol. 4). American Research Institution for Development.
- Beauchemin, J. & Fahny, E. (2014). *The meaning of History: Towards a rethinking of the History and Citizenship Education Program in Secondary III & IV*. Nigeria Ibadan.
- Bruner, J. (1960). *The Process of Education*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University press.
- Farrant, J.S. (1980) *Principles and practices of Education*. Burnt Mill, Harlow: Longman group UK Ltd.
- Gwanfobe, M. (2011). Africa's triple education heritages: a historical comparison. In Nsamenang, A. B. & Tchombe, T. *Handbook of African Educational Theories and Practice: A generative teacher education curriculum*(pp. 39-54). Bamenda: HDRC
- Miriama, C. et al (2013). *Education and Teaching*. Wellington: Career Development and Employment
- Ngoh, V.J. (1995) *History of Cameroon since 1800*. Cameroon: Limbe Presprint
- Nsamenang, A.B (2004). *The Teaching Learning Transaction: An Africentric Approach to Educational Psychology*. Bamenda: Human Development Resource Centre
- Ntoh, T.E. (2015). *Effective pedagogy under the new pedagogic approach*. Bamenda: Unique Printer and Publishers.
- Rudin, H.R. (1938). *Germans in the Cameroons*. Yale University New Heavens.
- Shinn, Y.H. (1997). *Teaching Strategies, their use and effectiveness as perceived by teachers of agriculture: A national study*. Iowa state University. Digital Repository. Retrospective Thesis and Dissertation.
- Tambo, L.I. (2003). *Principles and Methods of Teaching: Application in Cameroon Schools*. Buea: Anucam Publisher.
- Tambo, L.I. (2012). *Principles and Methods of Teaching*. (2nded). Limbe: Presprint.
- Tchombe, T.M. (2009). *Psychological Parameters in Teaching*. Yaounde: Presse Universitaire D'Afrique
- Weiner, R.G (1995). *History: Teaching and Methods*. Document Resume, ED 387 402
- Wiyahnyuy, L. F. (2019). The Issue of Ineffective Teaching in Cameroon Public Secondary Schools. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.2, No.3, 564-574.